

STRATEGY FOR PRE - REPORTATION

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ANNOTATION It is believed that people have known translation since the beginning of languages, and people needed translators to communicate in their commercial relations, travel, and political conversations ¹. The supply and demand for electricity is increasing. The time itself demands it. Translation is a communicative tool that serves the spiritual needs of another people and creates an opportunity for artistic enjoyment of a work created in one language.

Nowadays, in simultaneous translation, the translator uses several strategies at the same time. The decision is usually made on a case-by-case basis. Linguistic and extralinguistic factors definitely affect this situation. In the process of simultaneous interpretation, the interpreter works with direct communication, so he must have high-speed translation technology, be able to demonstrate and apply his knowledge and skills ².

In this article, our main task is to study the cases and processes of using the strategy of "prediction" of simultaneous translation, and to highlight the stages and to draw scientific results.

Key words: Strategy, simultaneous translation, linguistic and extralinguistic , technology, psycholinguistic , prediction , transformation .

¹ Chrobak , Marzena (2013) , "[For A Tin Ingot : The Archaeology Of Oral Interpretation](#) " Przekładaniec . A Journal of Literary Translation (بالغة الانجليزية) (Special issue): 87:101 مورشف , mn [asl](#) fy 30 Oct 2020

² Finkelberg N.D. Arabic language. Theory and technology in Perevo. - Moscow: Vostochnaya kniga, 2010. - C .35.

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A probabilistic prediction strategy consists in the early detection of linguistic components of the text that will appear in individual output by the translator. Thus, in some cases, the simultaneous interpreter can determine which verb will be in the original text before it appears in speech. The prediction strategy in the translation literature is described as a strategy applied mainly to constructions where the verb is in the final position or when the main nominal concept is at the end of the semantic group ⁴.

The term "probabilistic forecasting" was first coined by IMFeigenberg:

"The occurrence of state A is the maximum conditional probability of occurrence of signal B in order to prepare the organism's system for a reaction corresponding to such a state. The wider the range of events that have been observed equally frequently in the past (that is, the more uncertain the forecast), the greater the range of physiological systems mobilized in response to the signal A, which can be called probabilistic prediction" (Chernov 1978). :63).

The GIChernov prediction mechanism is a basic and important psycholinguistic mechanism that provides simultaneous translation (Chernov 1978:54). In a number of works of physiologists and psychologists, the probabilistic prediction strategy underlies many aspects of human mental activity, including speech activity. During the perception of the original speech by the

³ Finkelberg N.D. Arabic language. Theory and technology in Perevo. - Moscow: Vostochnaya kniga, 2010. - C .35.

⁴ Schweitzer A. D. Translation and linguistics. Three. write for institutes and faculties . - M., Voenizdat, 1973. - P.272.

synchronist, his brain creates various options to fulfill the communicative intentions of the author.

It should not be forgotten that it begins to appear after acquiring talent and potential as a result of a number of practical activities. Experienced translator prof. Sh. Shomusarov shared the following experience from his practice:

<p>Dear Rector, Tashkent State University of Oriental Studies has been educating scientists working in various fields, including translators and pedagogues, for several years now.</p> <p>We hope that improving prospective relations with Cairo University, exchange of teachers and students between universities will be mutually beneficial.</p>	<p>عزيزي السيد رئيس جامعة طشقند الحكومية للدراسات الشرقية تقوم بتدريب العلماء في مختلف المجالات ، بما في ذلك المترجمين والتربويين لعدة سنوات حتى الآن.</p> <p>نأمل أن يكون تحسين العلاقات الواحدة مع جامعة القاهرة ، وتبادل المعلمين والطلاب بين الجامعات ذات فائدة مزدوجة</p>
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The translator stated that "due to the limited time of the parties, they also benefited from excessive length of the translation. For this purpose, as I was well aware of the topic being raised and the interests of the parties, I started the translation before the end of the speaker's words. The conversation did not last long, and the parties were able to come to an agreement at the level they were interested in." ⁵.

In the process of communication between joint communicants, it is carried out through a language mediator - a simultaneous interpreter. Within the framework of

⁵ The interview disc from Sh. Shomusarov is presented in iova.

the linguistic theory of translation, LS Barkhudarov considers translation as an act of interlingual transformation (Barkhudarov 1975:6), so the translation researcher has the opportunity to simulate this process. GVChernov also looks at the joint project from a process perspective to create probabilistic prediction models. In the framework of such models, the translation of texts as a work of speech varies based on internal possibilities, i.e., a number of concepts such as consideration of equivalence, alternative - specialists engaged in the theory and practice of translation are developing universal rules of prediction.

distinguish ⁶two types of probabilistic prediction :

a) "linguistic" or "syntactic" prediction, which is based on predicting the source of discourse continuation, from a standard set of word rhymes and fixed phrases, i.e. *under take an obligation to* builds on knowledge from things like *...leave without a leg to stand on ...* to function words and conjunctions;

b) "Extralinguistic" ("non-scientific") prediction is based on external knowledge, extralinguistic information that the simultaneous interpreter has, or specific cognitive components.

Lederer suggests that there are 3 factors that enable probabilistic prediction (1981:248-249):

a) translator by language structure in advance familiar _

b) the words acceptance to do almost unnecessary to the event spinning of thoughts makes sense consistency ;

c) translator by the same to the moment until listened to , only head _ words _ with expressed of the speaker makes sense thoughts knee

Thus, when training translators, as well as learning translation strategies, it should be taken into account that strategies are not, as a rule, used in isolation, but in a complex way. Thus, probabilistic prediction decompression strategy, mixed

⁶ H. Hamidov, N. Ismatullayeva, S. Ergasheva. Simultaneous interpretation (tutorial). -Tashkent: TDSH U , 20 20 . b. 42.

strategy with trial and error strategy, and stopping strategy with waiting strategy can also be used together because they complement each other and contribute to improve translation quality.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it should be said that in the process of simultaneous interpretation, the interpreter works with direct communication, so he can have highly accelerated translation technology, can demonstrate his knowledge and skills, and may should take it. A probabilistic prediction strategy consists in the early detection of linguistic components of the text that will appear in individual output by the translator. Thus, in some cases, the simultaneous interpreter can determine which verb will be in the original text before it appears in speech. In addition, since the strategy is a means of achieving adequacy and alternation in translation from the source language to the target language, several strategies can be used simultaneously by the simultaneous interpreter.

List of used literature:

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